

Evaluating the Effects of Modernization on Karatig Jeepney in the City of Malolos, Bulacan

Angely E. Revilla¹ ,
Ma. Angela U. Brizuela⁴ ,
Gerilyn O. Estrella⁷

Authors Information:

¹⁻⁹ College Department Richwell Colleges,
Incorporated Plaridel, Bulacan, Philippines

Correspondence:

ddelacruz.pbcssi@gmail.com

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Abstract. This study examines the implications of modernization on the KaRaTig Jeepney in Malolos, Bulacan, emphasizing the balance between technological advancement and cultural preservation. The Philippine government's modernization program for public utility vehicles aims to improve environmental sustainability, passenger safety, and transportation efficiency; however, it also threatens the continued operation of traditional jeepneys, which serve as both a major mode of transportation and a cultural symbol in Filipino communities. While numerous studies have explored jeepney modernization, limited research has focused specifically on the KaRaTig Jeepney in Malolos, Bulacan. Using a descriptive qualitative research design, the study gathered data through interviews with seven drivers and six commuters to understand their experiences and perceptions regarding modernization. The findings revealed both positive and negative views toward the modernization program. Participants recognized the environmental benefits, improved safety, and enhanced comfort offered by modernized vehicles, yet they also expressed concerns about increased transportation fares, possible loss of livelihood among drivers, reduced accessibility for commuters, and the gradual disappearance of the KaRaTig Jeepney as part of the community's cultural identity. The study concludes that modernization efforts should not only prioritize technological progress but also consider the social, economic, and cultural realities of the people affected. Recommendations are therefore provided to support sustainable transportation development while preserving the heritage and cultural significance of the KaRaTig Jeepney in Malolos, Bulacan.

Keywords: Jeepneys, Karatig Jeepney, Modernization Program

Introduction

Transportation was an integral part of the tourism industry (Feng, et.al., 2023). On the top of that, one of the urban Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) targets was to ensure access to safe, affordable, accessible, and sustainable transport systems for all by 2030 (Fried et al., 2020). Jeepneys are significant form of transportation and an emblem in Filipino culture. During the American period, when American soldiers left over a cargo of jeepneys, the jeep's enculturation was one of the principal ways of transport in the Philippines. Furthermore, jeepneys have remained popular among Filipinos due to their distinctive exterior decorations, paintings, and sayings (Tus, 2021).

Meanwhile, in the city of Malolos, Bulacan, there was a jeepney embodying one of the cultural identities. Karatig jeep is a shorter version of the Sarao Public Utility Jeepney (PUJ), also known as "Hari ng Kalsada" (King of the Road) and a cultural emblem of Malolos. The Karatig jeep is highly significant for the city's riding public and for people who commute daily in adjacent places. He said that when tricycles were not yet available in the 1950s and early 1960s, the Karatig jeeps supplied local transportation in the town and neighboring areas (Estrope, 2025).

Modernization is vital to the growth of society and the economy today, with considerable technological developments that improve daily life. Moreover, the modernization of transportation systems may reduce isolation and offer a stimulus for growth in all aspects of life in society, including trade, industry, and other industries in all locations (Lanori, & Supriyanto, 2023). With all these concerns, the government decided to conduct Jeepney Modernization, in which the old standard jeepneys will be phased out and replaced with Electronic Jeepneys, or E-Jeepneys. The planned form of transportation is supposed to be environmentally clean and technologically advanced, making the Philippines worldwide competitive in the transportation system. Additionally, with the implementation of Modernized Jeepneys, Public Utility Drivers, Owners, Operators, and commuters are affected in a way that establishes job opportunities for them. Since not every Public Utility Vehicle (PUV) driver can afford the costs of converting traditional jeepneys to

modernized jeepneys and obtaining valid franchises due to difficulties in consolidating with corporations or cooperatives, it significantly effects Public Utility Vehicle (PUV) driver employment in the Philippines.

The researchers' primary aim is to evaluate the effects of modernization on the Karatig Jeepney in the City of Malolos, Bulacan. This scientific paper also wants to determine modernization's positive and negative effects on the Karatig jeepney. Additionally, this study wants to know the benefits of jeepney modernization to the commuters and drivers of Karatig Jeepneys. Furthermore, this study aims to propose a preservation plan.

The significance of this study was to evaluate the effects of modernization to the Karatig Jeepney in Malolos Bulacan and its culture preservation for the Capital of Bulacan. This study can help analyze and determine the negative and positive effects of the jeepney modernization program imposed by the government. The current scientific paper will have significance to the new body of knowledge since there are no studies with regard to the Karatig Jeepney Modernization.

Research Questions

The intention of the study was to evaluate the effects of Modernization to the Karatig Jeepney in the City of Malolos, Bulacan. Specifically, the research will seek answers to the following questions:

1. What are effects of Modernization to the Karatig Jeepneys in terms of:
 - 1.1 Transportation industry;
 - 1.2 Jeepney Modernization;
 - 1.3 Accessibility;
 - 1.4 Cultural Significance of Karatig Jeepney; and
 - 1.5 Environmental aspect of Transportation?
2. Based on the findings of the study, what recommendations can be generated to preserve the Karatig Jeepney as a cultural emblem of the City of Malolos, Bulacan?

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study evaluates the effects of the modernization of Karatig Jeepneys on commuters and drivers in the City of Malolos, Bulacan, following the implementation of the Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program in 2024. It focuses exclusively on Karatig Jeepney drivers and passengers as primary stakeholders who directly experience the transition from traditional to modernized jeepneys, including minors who may require parental guidance during interviews. The study excludes jeepney operators, owners, and other transport routes such as Plaridel–Malolos tricycles, and does not cover financial aspects such as income or commuting expenses. Using a qualitative descriptive design, data will be gathered through semi-structured face-to-face interviews with validated guides and analyzed through thematic analysis involving coding, theme identification, refinement, and interpretation of findings.

Literature Review

Transportation Industry

Moreover, the term 'Transportation' denotes moving individuals from one location to another. Within tourism, transportation refers to the conveyance of visitors from residences to locations where tourist services are available. Tourists' perceptions of tourism products and their travel experiences commence and conclude with transportation. As Yusof et al. (2021) aver transportation is an indispensable aspect of tourism. The progress significantly influences the rapid expansion of the tourism industry in transportation technology, vehicles, infrastructure, and innovations. Notably, statistics from the World Tourist Organization reveal a remarkable shift and expansion in the tourism industry between 2005 and 2008. The advancement of transportation technology is poised to continue shaping the future of tourism in myriad ways. In addition, Transport has direct social repercussions, influencing and assuring movement. Travel time is crucial in deciding on a specific place for a vacation, especially in international tourism. Tourism has grown primarily due to transportation improvements Wendt, et al. (2021). Suppose national Transport encompasses transportation between communities or throughout a country. In that case, international transit refers to transportation that crosses at least a single territorial border, with the points of dispatch and location of the goods in distinct nations (Nugroho,2019). Because transportation is the initial expression of tourism consumption, its psychological influence on the visitor is critical in creating the best image of the tourist product. To put it another way, the tourist has the first encounter with the goods he has purchased through the travel agency (Yadav, Vashisth, & Desai, 2020). For a long time, the relevance of transportation as an essential component of the tourist system has been debated in the literature. Many writers attempted to assess the significance of transportation in tourist flows and its impact on state economies.

Jeepney Modernization

The modernization is only an improvement to the jeepney; it is simply a method of increasing the computer's safety. The only jeepneys that will be phased out are over a century old. Drivers should be relieved that jeepneys will become obsolete once modernization is done. The jeepney would not be phased out under the modernization scheme, according to Indong, Kilat, Lacquio, and Ballesteros, (2022) of the Land Transportation Franchising and Regulatory Board. They are simply determining which sort of jeepney will be presented. According to the Department of Transportation (2020), the cars will also have PWD-friendly features and free internet for commuters' comfort. The jeepneys will be manufactured and built locally. Jeepney modernization has been a prominent topic of discussion in the Philippines since the Marcos dictatorship (1965-1986), and it has resurfaced during the Duterte administration. Through the Department of Transportation (DOTr) Department Order No. 2017-011 or the Omnibus Guideline on the Planning and Identification of Public Road Transportation Services and Franchise Issuance (LTFRB, 2020), the Duterte government launched the PUVMP as one of its flagship programs aimed at a comprehensive system reform that will entirely change the public land transportation industry. Although jeepneys are essential to Philippine history, severe limitations and regulations are in place because of worries about their impact on environmental pollution. Traditional jeepney models have broken several regulations, including overcrowding and pollution. These infractions are problematic since they have led to health dangers, and by eliminating conventional jeepneys, violations like the ones described above might be considerably minimized. Following the government's trial runs, the general public will embrace the modified jeepneys since they believe they would be better for people and the environment in the long run (Cudis, 2019). In order to combat the environmental issues caused by vehicles, the Philippine government and DOTr issued Department Order No. 2017-011 (Re: Omnibus Guidelines on the Planning and Identification of Public Transportation Services and Franchise Issuance), also known as the Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program (PUVMP), which was launched in 2017. As mentioned by Atos, (2021) go on to say that the program aimed to make the country's public transportation systems more efficient and environmentally friendly by replacing old jeepneys with jeepneys that have a Euro-4 compliant engine or electric engine, which reduces the vehicle's contribution to pollution in the environment. As of May 2020, the LTFRB and DTI have submitted 16 prototype jeepneys that were domestically constructed per the DOTr requirements. These new jeepneys were designed to replace those 15 years or older, impacting the industry's longest-serving drivers and operators (Xu, et al., 2019).

Transportation Accessibility

Accessibility means easy access to facilities and activities, regardless of transportation mode or time frame. Su et al. (2023) proposed that prioritizing accessibility-oriented public transportation planning can lead to several benefits, including improved operational efficiency of public transit, orderly urban development, and reduced issues such as traffic congestion, environmental pollution, and resource consumption in large cities. These highlight the significance of accessibility in street design and public transportation planning. Access to transportation and urban infrastructure is fundamental for social and economic development. Accessibility, therefore, plays a crucial role in shaping urban and transport planning fields. Its significance lies in ensuring that everyone, regardless of physical or socio-economic limitations, can access and benefit from the built environment (Tsumita et al. (2023), with research frequently focusing on individual cities as mentioned by Su et al. (2023), modeling and calculating the accessibility of public transportation stations in a town, and evaluating the development of public transportation in that city, as stated by Pirra et al. (2022), thereby effectively addressing problems such as traffic congestion, environmental pollution, and resource constraints. Furthermore, the level of accessibility has a significant direct and indirect impact on the urban setting it serves. Although the concept of accessibility encompasses similar dimensions across studies, its implementation varies significantly depending on the research or policy need, mode of transport, data availability (Wu & Levinson, 2020), and also the type of activity because people plan their transportation differently for work, education, health, and leisure activities (Ramos et al., 2020). According to Zhu et al. (2023), positive accessibility implementations based on observed behaviors may help assess access levels to opportunities, allowing for person-specific considerations. In contrast, normative accessibility implementations based on desirable access levels may be particularly interesting for inequality and social exclusion assessments and policymaking. Most accessibility analyses evaluate (uneven) access to employment opportunities as a proxy for a variety of other urban options or amenities, either because it is associated with many daily urban trips, according to many origin-destination surveys around the world, or because it is directly related to an individual's income and quality of life in the current political-economic system. Indeed, some research has linked a lack of public transportation accessibility to increased job challenges (Bastiaanssen et al., 2020). Puccini et al. (2023) discuss economic disadvantages and social marginalization. Long and expensive daily commutes have a severe influence on the poor's capacity to obtain

and maintain formal employment, particularly on women and some racial groups (Bittencourt, & Giannotti, 2021).

Cultural Significance of KaRaTig Jeepney

Nowhere else in the world, preserved for the Philippines, were Jeepneys discovered. This vehicle epitomizes Filipino innovation, inventiveness, flexibility, and tenacity. It is a bold, colorful, fearless solution to mass transportation challenges. No two jeepneys are alike. Each jeepney was customized with different patterns, images, and text. From the abilities of artisans in body-building to the talents of artists in customized painting, the owner, as well as the driver, buys or manufactures decorations, accessories and hand-paints the inscriptions throughout the years; consequently, the upshot is a highly individualized assemblage (Tugano, 2021). Moreover, the jeepney has been a vital feature of the Philippine transportation system since its origin, particularly in urban and rural regions where it serves as the principal method of public transportation (Andalecio et al., 2020). The jeepney is a common form of transportation for commuters, especially those with limited resources, due to its accessibility, cost, and capacity to fit through small streets. Furthermore, Parrucho and Padullo (2023) say the jeepney symbolizes Philippine culture and identity. Jeepney has significance in creating a life in the Philippines while also serving as a cultural object for its accessories and the attitudes of its passengers, owners, and drivers (Behrens et al., 2021). Furthermore, this public utility vehicle (PUV) is classified as paratransit, which refers to creative forms of mobility when available transportation fails to meet the demands of the commuting public. In contrast, a jeepney is a type of transportation without predetermined stops and depends on the passengers' requests or needs (Mills, Tortez, & Blanton, 2019). In addition to that, as a cultural emblem, jeepneys are known for their noisy designs and engines. Jeepney drivers and owners paint their vehicles with bright colors and tacky ornaments to tell a tale. These narratives frequently include references to family members working abroad, nature scenes from a family's original province and heritage, basketball players, and cartoons highlighting Filipino obsession with Western pop culture in the post-colonial period (Mateo-Babiano et al., 2020). Also, if there is one vehicle that defines the Philippine mass transportation system or the Philippine cultural identity in general, it will have to be the "jeepney." Its undoubted capability to transport passengers as economically and conveniently as possible manifests how technology plays a massive role in developing new products and processes that contribute to human activity and shape an identity that reflects ideals and aspirations (Rabino, 2021). Moreover, jeepneys are a unique transportation that can only be found in the Philippines. Its physical form symbolizes Filipinos' rich culture, with hanging quotation phrases, bright graphics, and religious icons. Also, the attitudes of its passengers—saying 'para po' and 'bayad po', with commuters clinging on to steel railings beside the stairs (sabit). However, behind the qualities thereof, the ruling class has made a significant contribution to the existence of jeepneys for many years, with the poorest of the poor preferring this mode of transportation, as highlighted by Florenda (2022).

Environmental Aspects of Transportation

Transitioning to cleaner technology and providing public transportation services are critical steps in addressing the climate issue and achieving mobility equity, particularly in the Global South. However, while low-carbon transportation is integral to this need, the transition process must be fair and not disenfranchise thousands of informal transport workers who would be badly impacted by state transport modernization initiatives, as highlighted by Gatarin (2023). Sustainable urban transportation systems promote accessibility, affordability, safety, fairness, efficiency, and economic viability while reducing emissions and other environmental consequences (Sdoukopoulos, Pitsiava-Latinopoulou, Basbas, & Papaioannou, 2019; Sultana et al., 2019). These systems deal with social, economic, and environmental challenges in a balanced manner. In addition to that, urbanization growth creates new transportation needs and encourages transportation development, resulting in a shift in urban spatial form. Transportation plays a critical role in affecting urbanization levels because of the necessity to overcome space and time constraints, as highlighted by Liu and Su (2021). In line also with this, environmental concerns about air quality and emissions of greenhouse gas (GHG) from burning fossil fuels have driven several governments and areas to seek more sustainable ways of transportation. Electric vehicles (EVs) have emerged as a highly promising technology predicted to play a significant part in the energy transition to a sustainable transportation system over the next several decades (Agaton et al., 2020). Jeepney manufacturers employ refurbished or overhauled Japanese engines attached to newly constructed PUJ bodies. Following Tiglao (2020), the general perception of a jeepney is that it is old, inefficient, and known for emitting smoke and that older cars consume more gasoline, which increases the danger of air pollution from exhaust gas. Also, diesel-fed jeepneys used for public transport contribute to 15% of the particulate matter (PM) emissions and 11% of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions in Metro Manila, based on the IES Philippines Study (Kecorius et al., 2019). Issues involving the harmful contributions of the fossil fuel-dominated transportation sector to the climate crisis are becoming more prominent in legislative and regulatory discussions. Eliminating outmoded, dilapidated, and polluting

paratransit networks in many Global South countries continues to elicit strong emotions and endangers the livelihoods of thousands of informal transportation workers. This is predicated on the assumption that these paratransit services will eventually be replaced, albeit this has not occurred in many cases worldwide, as Gatarin observes (2021).

Methodology

Research Design

The research study used a descriptive qualitative method. This method allows the researchers to gather in-depth insights and understand the experiences, emotions, and perspectives of commuters and Karatig jeepney drivers. The information will be gathered through qualitative research to help identify the effects of modernization of the Karatig jeepney in the in the City of Malolos, Bulacan.

Sampling Design

The study used purposive sampling because it specifically selects participants who have direct experience and knowledge of the Karatig Jeepney modernization program. This method is appropriate as it ensures that only relevant commuters and drivers in the City of Malolos, Bulacan are included, allowing the researchers to gather meaningful and in-depth information.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in the City of Malolos, Bulacan, where Karatig Jeepney routes operate and where the implementation of the Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program is actively experienced. This location was chosen because it is the primary area where both drivers and commuters directly encounter the effects of jeepney modernization.

Research Participants

The researchers study used purposive sampling technique. The general sample is composed of thirteen (13) participants, seven (7) of whom are commuters and six (6) drivers of the Karatig jeepneys affected by the government's modernization program. These participants can provide accurate responses to evaluate the effects of the modernization program on the Karatig jeepney in the City of Malolos, Bulacan.

Research Instrument

This study utilized semi-structured interview which was composed of specific set of questions in eliciting responses of the participants. The interview content was composed of five (5) parts about the effects of modernization program on Karatig Jeepney in the City of Malolos, Bulacan. The major parts contain one question in which probing questions facilitated to allow interviewees explicate responses. Audio recorded application from smartphones was used to ensure in getting authentic responses. After completion of all interviews, the researchers cross-checked each other's recordings to ascertain the validity and reliability of the information collected. In addition, secondary data were also used to gain more information, or supplement or validate data collected in fieldwork during interviews.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers went directly to the Local Government Unit of the City of Malolos, Bulacan, to seek information and ask questions about Karatig jeepneys, as the officials within their jurisdiction were the ones who promoted the modernization program. They also sought permission from the association of Karatig Jeepney groups and commuters. Throughout the research procedure, selective participation of all participants with informed consent was observed to ensure that they were provided with a thorough description of the study methodology and complete assistance during the conduct of the study. The researchers conducted semi-structured face-to-face interviews with the participants, which were answered based on their perspectives. During the interviews, the researchers recorded and documented the participants' responses, which were essential for data analysis. The refusal of participants to engage in the study was respected, especially when participation was perceived to potentially lead to incrimination or a violation of their right to privacy.

Results and Discussions

Research Question 1: What are effects of Modernization to the Karatig Jeepneys in terms of Transportation industry, Jeepney Modernization, Accessibility, Cultural Significance of Karatig Jeepney, and Environmental aspect of Transportation?

Transportation Industry

The researchers came up with this theme based on the key informants about the effects of Modernization on the Karatig Jeepney in the City of Malolos, Bulacan in terms of the Transportation Industry.

Following the government's Modernization program's execution, the illustrated transportation sector themes. The transportation sector plays a critical role in the lives of drivers and commuters. The renovation of the Karatig Jeepney can impact a region's transportation sector by increasing the number of more readily available jeepneys to commuters. The market's strong demand and limited supply of upgraded Karatig jeepneys also benefit the transportation sector. This subject can assist the nation in promoting the public transportation sector. The Karatig jeepney is changing due to the public's need for accessible transportation, while the government is being phase-out of its use. One of the participants acknowledged that the implementation of the Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program (PUVMP) had an effect on the Karatig Jeepney transportation business in the City of Malolos, Bulacan, particularly on air pollution. Thus, this implies that the government imposed the modernization will help the environment to lessen the air pollution that omits by the traditional jeepney. It also implies that modernized jeepney is one of the key factors to lessen the harmful gas omitted from jeepney. As quoted by a participant:

"I noticed that the fare is lower compared to modern jeepneys, but the modern jeepney helps with air pollution."

This demonstrates that the government provides solutions for environmental issues. One participant said, "The modern jeepney helps with air pollution." The claim the present study to reduce air pollution and enhance public transportation; the government began a modernization program that required jeepney engines to meet international standards (Estrellado, 2020). However, achieving ecologically sustainable transportation is more than just removing smoke; the lives of 2.4 million Filipinos are at risk. Furthermore, on the excuse of environmental harm and safety concerns about traditional jeepneys, the government initiated its Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program (PUVMP) in 2017 (Mendoza, 2021).

The change in the Karatig Jeepney following the implementation of the Jeepney Modernization Program was explained in this theme. The government's modernization initiative impacts the Malolos' traditional jeepney business, particularly the Karatig model. Additionally, this clarifies how the underprivileged can utilize the updated jeepneys available to all Malolos, Bulacan residents. Furthermore, this states that commuters and drivers must adhere to the government's adopted scheme. Because it is mandatory, all people, including commuters and drivers, must comply with the upgrading program. Furthermore, this demonstrates that implementing the Modernization program will lessen the frequency of the Karatig jeepney. Table 6 clearly shows that commuters and driver informants are caught between coping and not coping with the government's policy. This also shows that drivers might become colorum on the streets if they do not obey official laws. Withal, the people must comply with the government policies. As quoted by the participant:

"I can't do anything; it's the government that implements it."

In accordance with this, remarked that the phase-out of public utility vehicles older than 15 years is consistent with the modernization goals of transportation-related government entities to enhance commuter safety and convenience (Villalino, 2018). Furthermore, the drivers are still determined since the government's modernization program has a negative impact on the drivers (Adaya, 2020). Furthermore, as this study demonstrates the paucity of options available to drivers. If they do not comply, they can lose their livelihood. Another responder expressed concern about the potential financial catastrophe operators would face due to the adoption (Atos, 2021).

The Karatig jeepney is becoming less frequent as a result of modernization; however, there are still issues to be addressed before thoroughly implementing the modernization jeepney in the City of Malolos, Bulacan. Furthermore, the Karatig jeepney is accessible to Malolos residents since the narrow roads can reduce traffic because Karatig jeepneys are smaller than the modernized jeepney offered. Moreover, some participants implied that the modernization program did not affect the Karatig jeepney transportation industry since Karatig was the only type of jeepney compatible with the city's narrow roads. As mentioned by the participant:

"Perhaps for now, based on what I see, the Karatig are becoming less frequent. As a commuter, we also find it difficult to ride, now with modernization and the phase-out, the Karatig jeepneys are also becoming less frequent or are being reduced."

This claim was supported by study, which stated that the legendary jeeps are the cheapest way to commute in our country; picking up and dropping off is too easy for both passengers and drivers; they can stop anywhere; however, traffic congestion on our roads is unbearable, with passengers in the middle of the streets blocking the way of other drivers who endanger others (Arcieto et al., 2022).

Additionally, Modernized jeepney on Karatig Jeepney in the City of Malolos has negative effects on its commuters and drivers. Bulacan is based on the economic reasons. It explains that if the Karatig jeepney

will be phase out the fare will increase. Also, the modernized jeepney we're not suitable for rentals due to its features. It will suffer also the drivers since they will become unemployed. With that, some of the participants quoted that they not agreed on the modernization program due to fare hike. According to the participant:

"I will not agree to replace the Karatig because the fare will increase, they said it would now be 50 pesos, who knows if they will reduce it, we will be miserable."

In a study, proponents of jeepney modernization refuse to accept the reality that high-priced modern jeepneys would result in high jeepney rates (Mendoza, 2021). Furthermore, study claims that worsening privatization and corporatization threaten to boost jeepney fares by 300% to 400% in the following years (IBON, 2023). Furthermore, a contemporary jeepney-led fee increase has a domino effect on drivers and passengers (Mariano, 2020).

The modernization program slowly killing the traditional jeepneys. Moreover, the karatig jeepney is part of every citizen of Malolos lives. It describes how the karatig jeepneys are important to the history and culture of the citizens of the city of Malolos. Withal, the citizens of the Malolos did not agree to replace the cultural-historical jeepney called Karatig. This also implies that the Maloleños become drastic since that is the cultural emblem of the city of Malolos. Furthermore, the local executive and its members were trying to push the Karatig jeepney to become a tourist jeepney in the city. As quoted by the participant:

"Of course, what people have grown accustomed to will disappear. The familiar Karatig they knew will change. Naturally, it will appear new to the eye, and as someone from Malolos, it's sad for us that the Karatig will be gone, especially for me, whose route passes through Paseo del Congreso, where the road is so narrow that only the Karatig can fit."

Align with this claims, it is parallel to the study of this study will interpret material culture through the jeepney, a medium symbolizing current social and cultural values (Zheng, 2023). Added to that, cultural obstacles should also be included in the list, as heritage activists are concerned about the aesthetic value of jeepneys, which have become a symbol of Philippine culture and arts (Agaton, 2019).

Transfer of Burden to the Drivers and Commuters due to Modernized Jeepney

The themes and codes identified from the data transcript—the obtained theme centered on the effects of the modernization of the Karatig jeepney on commuters and drivers. It also explains why jeepneys are essential to its people because it is a public transportation jeepney that is readily available to the public and contributes to the promotion of our nation. Furthermore, it produces jobs and transports people to their workplaces or destinations. More importantly, jeepneys contribute significantly to the lives of commuters and drivers.

The commuters prefer Karatig for a ride because it is essential to the lives of every Maloleños. This also implies that commuters find alternative public transportation difficult since it is the only jeepney that can enter the Paseo Del Congreso Road in Malolos, Bulacan. Furthermore, the Karatig jeepneys were scare due to the modernization program. Moreover, the Karatig jeepneys routes are in just two ways that is why the commuters choose to ride Karatig. Withal, commuters preferred Karatig jeepney due to its availability. As mentioned by the participant:

"Yes! With the modernization, there are jeepney drivers who find it difficult to keep up because they need to upgrade, especially with what our government wants to implement. As a commuter, Karatig is becoming scarce, so it's challenging for us to catch a ride. For the drivers, they need to adapt because the increase desired by the government for fares is not that significant."

This claim was supported of the study which stated that traditional jeepneys are the most economical and budget-friendly transportation, with rates starting at 7 to 8 pesos (Ong, 2023) . Furthermore, jeepneys are the most popular public transportation in the Philippines, particularly along major arterial roads, due to their ease, accessibility, and minimized fare (De Oliveira, 2021).

Furthermore, the commuters are affected by the higher fare scheme. Since commuters are the ones who ride jeepneys to go to their destinations, this also implies that people are affected by the fare getting expensive once the modernized jeepneys operate in the entire Malolos.

The study's findings present that the government's modernization program significantly affects commuters. Additionally, commuters was can't afford the fare of the upgrade jeepney. As quoted by some participant:

"Everyone will be affected, not just the drivers but also the passengers, because the fare will increase. With the high price of diesel, you can no longer lower the fare. The minimum in the rotation is 13, and the minimum for the modern is much higher."

The findings of the study was backed with the claimed that commuters have a significant say in the fare they pay (Atos, 2021). Additionally, as a study proposed, the government should raise base fares to

entice transport operators and potential investors to embrace the PUV modernization program (Agaton, 2019).

This implies that commuters prefer to ride on Karatig jeepney than modernized jeepney. In addition, the commuters also choose to ride Karatig due to higher fare schemes which impact the lives of every commuter.

Withal, the effects of modernization on its drivers, wherein the drivers were affected by this transition. This theme focused on the drivers that can be explained through the experiences of drivers' lives after the modernization program's implementation. Additionally, it explains the significance of the Karatig jeepney to the lives of Maloleños. The theme contextualized that drivers are affected by modernization since it's their job. This theme includes sub-theme Difficulty of Karatig Jeepney Drivers modernizing; Government Policies affecting the Drivers and Possible Unemployment of Karatig Drivers.

Furthermore, in a study, mentioned that the jeepney drivers showcased negative perception towards public utility vehicles modernization program (Atos, 2021). This study supported the findings of this study because according to the participant:

"Yes, there is. It will have a significant impact because, instead of the day's earnings going entirely to the drivers for their personal income, what happens with modernization is it gets divided. For commuters, it depends on how much they set the price."

This implies that the modernization program implemented by the government has negative effects to the lives of the Karatig jeepney drivers. A study coined that more than the revenue of drivers and operators will be required to cover the cost of a new unit. Furthermore, if drivers and operators can afford a unit by taking out a loan, they would spend all their earnings to repay their obligations (Manuel, 2019). Moreover, the program has faced opposition from jeepney drivers and operators, who say that the modernization effort would result in job losses and the migration of many small operators (Mendoza, 2021)

The key Jeepney driver informants have had negative experiences with the Public Utility Vehicles Modernization Program (PUVMP). This implies that the drivers need to follow the proposed program implemented by the government. The respondent stated:

"Of course, commuters will face difficulties, especially in such cases. As for the drivers, it will have a significant impact on us. We could lose our jobs because of this."

This suggests that unemployment has had a considerable impact on the lives of all drivers. Furthermore, the drivers' money will be directed into the updated jeep. Furthermore, scientific study state that while Filipinos are optimistic about the Public Utility Vehicles Modernization Program (PUVMP), they are concerned about job losses for Traditional Public Utility Jeepney (TPUJ) drivers if Modernized Public Utility Jeepneys (MPUJs) replace Traditional Public Utility Jeepneys (TPUJs) (Amorsolo & Cabatingan, 2021).

The modernization program is very challenging to the lives of every drivers. This can cause challenges in terms of financial implications and potential disruptions in the livelihood of the traditional jeepney drivers. It signifies that the drivers are affected by the transition on the public utility jeepney. Moreover, the commuters faced difficulties since that is their preference to choose Karatig due to its low fare. For the drivers, it affects the lives of the drivers. According to the participant:

"Yes, because most Karatig drivers are elderly, they might not find other work due to their age. As a commuter, it's challenging to find alternative public transportation. If I pay for a tricycle, it's more expensive, but if I only pay for a Karatig jeep, it costs just 13 pesos to get to a place within Malolos City."

This assertion was consistent with the findings of study who said that modernization may result in employment and company losses (Guno et. al., 2021). Furthermore, research found that the worry of losing their livelihood among jeepney drivers and operators is echoed by thousands of other workers whose livelihoods are also related to the sector (Bautista, 2023).

This implies that the transition affects the lives of Karatig jeepney workers and commuters.

The Effects of Modernization to the Karatig Jeepneys in terms of Accessibility

The modernization initiative is still one of the major concerns affecting Filipinos, particularly the Maloleños, who have traditionally ridden the Karatig jeepney as part of their daily lives. Additionally, understanding the management of the work pattern of the transportation system is very urgent and accessible; it is necessary to have a broad view and also see the negative side of the modernization of the transportation system in human life so that they have an objective point of view if transportation services are not managed with good transportation management or are not used for good purposes (Herjanto, 2019). On top of that, the updated jeepney was inaccessible to Malolos residents because of the small roads and their opposition to the phase-out of Karatig. The participant of the present study stated:

"The new jeepney nowadays is not accessible. Firstly, among the issues, the owners of these modern jeepneys, even just the parts themselves, are very expensive. Unlike these kinds of vehicles, they are really cheap, truly for the masses, and the fare price is also not too high, so anyone can afford it, unlike those in modern ones where even just a few kilometers would mean high prices."

This implies that the modernized jeepney is not accessible to all citizens, specifically in the City of Malolos, Bulacan. This study parallels the study of who found that traditional jeepneys are the most accessible and affordable public transportation in urban areas of the Philippines (Ong, 2023). Also, a study pointed out, jeepney as public transport gives convenience to commuters (Samarra, et.al., 2023).

Moreover, the government should take to create and implement policies for using updated jeepneys. This implies that the government must create plans that provides the community a clear stand and implementation of the Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program (PUVMP). As a result, upgraded jeepneys are being implemented before becoming widely available. This highlights the significance of making upgraded jeepneys easily accessible to drivers and commuters. As mentioned by a participant:

"The new jeepney nowadays is not affordable. Firstly, among the issues, the owners of these modern jeepneys, even just the parts themselves, are very expensive. Unlike these kinds of vehicles, they are really cheap, truly for the masses, and the fare price is also not too high, so anyone can afford it, unlike those in modern ones where even just a few kilometers would mean high prices"

This claims was supported by a research that the status of transport as public services and transport policy orientation should be identified by a basic law for transport as well as clarifying the developing direction of "innovation, coordination, green openness and sharing" (Malasique, et. al., 2023). Furthermore, it is suggested to establish a systematic, authoritative public transport policy-making procedure through legislation. In addition, transport stakeholders are still hesitant to adopt e-PUVs due to high investment costs, lack of technical and policy support, skepticism on strict implementation of the programs, and public acceptance (Bastiaanssen, et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the City of Malolos is yet to have a modern jeepney, indicating that the implementation of modern jeepneys in the city is still incomplete. Moreover, it highlights the urgent need for more modernized jeepneys in Malolos. This implies that the production of modern jeepneys is still ongoing. The present study's findings are supported by the study below.

"Not! Because there are still modern ones passing by, many still patronize the traditional jeepneys because the fare is higher, and then it's like there aren't too many modern jeepneys nowadays."

Indeed, several studies have connected a lack of public transportation access to increasing employment problems (Bastiaanssen, et al., 2020).. Added to that, the current public transportation system in the Philippines has been deemed inconvenient to daily commuters and public utility operators due to traffic congestion and a lack of public vehicles for commuters, resulting in longer transportation times and hassle rides (Malasique, et. al., 2023).

The drivers cannot afford to buy the proposed modernized jeepney. Withal, the modernized jeepney is expensive for the masses especially to the drivers and commuters. It can be seen that there will be a domino effect when it comes to the modernization program from its jeepney to fares and to the entire economy. Withal, it becomes burden to the jeepney drivers and commuters. As quoted by the participant:

"The accessibility of modernized jeepneys for both drivers and passengers is influenced by factors such as affordability, infrastructure, and transition assistance. Despite the aim of improving services through modernization, potential financial challenges for drivers and fare adjustments may create hardships for some commuters. Establishing inclusive policies and support systems is crucial to enhance the accessibility of modernized jeepneys for both drivers and passengers."

This result was similarly mentioned in a research study. It would be better if the jeepneys were upgraded and fixed instead of buying the expensive modernized jeepneys (Atos, et, al., 2021). Furthermore, traditional jeepneys are the most widely utilized and least expensive public method of transportation in the Philippines, as well as the most prevalent mode of transportation (Carriere, 2022). Moreover, the government must provide more lavish subsidies and finances to transport workers in rehabilitating traditional jeepneys. Similarly, the government must provide other incentives (e.g., capacity strengthening, livelihood support) rather than phasing out traditional jeepneys in favor of expensive imported vehicles (Atienza, 2023).

The modern jeepneys in their current form need to be better-suited for the roads of Malolos City. The challenging terrain and other factors have made it difficult for these vehicles to operate safely and efficiently. However, it is essential to note that this issue does only sometimes applies to all some of the roads in the region.

Furthermore, it should be emphasized that upgrading to a more suitable vehicle model is a costly process for both drivers and operators. As such, this change should be supported by the public, who believe in the government's vision and are willing to help drive progress forward. By coming together and supporting this vital initiative, citizens and government can ensure that Malolos City's roads are safer and more efficient for everyone.

"No, because some roads in Malolos are narrow, so modern jeeps are not accessible to me inside Malolos."

This study indicates that by connecting modernity and minimum effort, suitable and accessible alternatives to adversity may be increased, including low-cost public transportation (Lander, 2018). Also, among the significant components of the Public Utility Vehicles Modernization Program (PUVMP) is fleet modernization, which entails modernizing the Public Utility Vehicles (PUVs) or Public Utility Jeepneys (PUJs) to achieve a comfortable, accessible, reliable, environmentally friendly, and sustainable (C.A.R.E.S.) with due consideration for people with disabilities (PWDs) and the elderly.

Karatig Jeepney as a Cultural Emblem of Maloleños

The importance of Karatig jeepney in terms of accessibility, culture, economy, and policy. This theme's social and cultural aspects highlight jeepneys' advantages and disadvantages for society and its people. Specifically, it explores how the replacement of traditional jeepneys with modern ones could impact the lives of drivers and passengers. Moreover, it describes how modernization has affected Philippine society and culture. Jeepneys, a significant cultural symbol and a vital source of employment in the country, play a crucial role in this chapter. This emphasizes the significant role of Karatig jeepneys in the daily lives of the people of Malolos. Moreover, it has been suggested that removing Karatig jeepneys from service could worsen the traffic situation in the city due to the narrow roads. According to the participant:

"It's important because it's become a trademark of Malolos. Only here you'll find karatig jeepneys. If they disappear and other types of vehicles take their place, it will worsen the traffic, which is already bad."

This claim was supported by the study that in the 20th century, the changes of transportation began as focuses on the accessibility, mobility and safety of the vehicles (Andelecio, et. al., 2020). Transportation has helped people to reach their desired destinations faster argue that (Gumasing, 2021).

In addition, the Karatig jeepney serves as more than just a mode of transportation in Malolos, Bulacan. It is a vital component of the community, integral to the daily routines of all residents. Beyond its practicality, the Karatig jeepney holds significant cultural importance, representing the city's identity, spirit, and resilience. The data confirms this reality, underscoring the indispensable role that Karatig jeepneys play in the daily lives of Malolos' citizens. As quoted by the participant:

"The traditional jeepneys in Malolos, known as karatig jeepneys, hold significant cultural value beyond their role as transportation. Prior to modernization, these vehicles were integral to local culture, embodying the unique identity and traditions of the community. They represent more than just transportation; they symbolize communal connections. Introducing modern jeepneys could potentially bring changes to the culture. While modernization aims for efficiency and safety improvements, it's crucial to preserve the cultural significance of traditional karatig jeepneys. Striking a balance between change and cultural heritage is important in maintaining a sense of identity and connection to the community."

Jeepneys are public vehicles that are popularly used for transportation in the Philippines. Furthermore, jeepneys represent the value of being Filipino on how the culture in its every transportation goes (known as Bayanihan) and how it can be an image of peoples' art because of its unique exterior design, as mentioned (Adaya, 2020).

Moreover, noted that the City of Malolos is a historic site with a strong traditional culture. Karatig jeepneys are a cultural symbol of Malolos and play an essential role in the city. Malolos' cultural identity is being eroded as a result of urban industrialization (Estacio, 2022).

Jeepney is ingrained in Filipino culture, identity, values, and the nation's streets. This study was supported by a research, it not only represents the "King of the Road" and the "moving icon of the Philippine culture," but it also exemplifies the inventiveness, creativity, craftsmanship, and entrepreneurship of the Filipino people (Parrucho, 2023). Furthermore, a study stated that the unique Sarao Jeepney is undoubtedly a part of Filipino identity due to its brilliant and vivid ornamentation. The jeepney reflected Filipino characteristics, such as faith and belief in life (Angeles, & Frisnedi, 2021).

Furthermore, the economic significance of the Karatig jeepney in Malolos, which cannot be overstated. The jeepney has become an integral part of the city's local economy, enabling people to move around the city quickly and at an affordable cost. The low fare charged by Karatig jeepney is an added advantage for the citizens, who can save some money on transportation costs while using this service. It is

worth noting that the Karatig jeepney has created job opportunities for many people in Malolos. The drivers, conductors, and mechanics who operate and maintain the jeepneys earn their livelihood through this service. As a result, the jeepney has become an essential source of income for many families in the area. Aside from the economic benefits, the Karatig jeepney also serves as a means of fostering community and social interaction. As quoted by a participant:

"The karatig is a big help for us because first and foremost, it helps us save money, and secondly, we're already accustomed to riding that type of vehicle."

This study was supported by a study which stated that the amount of money jeepney drivers earn is sometimes insufficient to support their families; thus, if the Public Utility Vehicles Modernization Program (PUVMP) is fully implemented and jeepney drivers take out loans to pay for replacement jeepneys, the additional debt will deprive them of necessities (Manuel, 2019). As a result, many people believe the policy is anti-poor because it is difficult for drivers and cooperatives to get funds for modernization (Tacderas).

In addition, the importance of preserving the iconic Karatig jeepney in Malolos. It discussed the need for the government to establish new policies to protect this unique jeepney model. The Karatig jeepney holds significant cultural and historical value to the people of Malolos, as it represents the transportation modernization in the area. It symbolizes pride for the community, and its preservation is crucial in reminding people of their heritage. Therefore, it is imperative to safeguard this precious vehicle for future generations to appreciate and admire.

"The traditional jeepneys in Malolos, known as karatig jeepneys, hold significant cultural value beyond their role as transportation. Prior to modernization, these vehicles were integral to local culture, embodying the unique identity and traditions of the community. They represent more than just transportation; they symbolize communal connections. Introducing modern jeepneys could potentially bring changes to the culture. While modernization aims for efficiency and safety improvements, it's crucial to preserve the cultural significance of traditional karatig jeepneys. Striking a balance between change and cultural heritage is important in maintaining a sense of identity and connection to the community."

This was supported by the research mentioned; a refined policy approach has been adopted to recognize the extent of transportation services in rural destinations to move to "more sustainable" modes of Transportation (Smith, Robbins, & Dickinson, 2019).. Also, Although the concept of accessibility encompasses similar dimensions across studies, its implementation varies significantly depending on the research or policy need, mode of transport, data availability (Levinson & Wu, 2020), and also the type of activity because people plan their transportation differently for work, education, health, and leisure activities (Ramos, 2020).

Research Question 2: Based on the findings of the study, what recommendations can be generated to preserve the Karatig Jeepney as a cultural emblem of the City of Malolos, Bulacan?

Based on the findings of the study, several preservation recommendations were generated to safeguard the Karatig Jeepney as a cultural emblem of Malolos, Bulacan. The proposed preservation plan emphasizes a multi-dimensional approach that integrates cultural awareness, historical documentation, policy advocacy, tourism development, community engagement, and intergenerational transmission of knowledge. Central to the plan is the goal of actively promoting the cultural significance of the Karatig Jeepney through awareness campaigns, advocacy for protective policies, restoration of existing units, and strengthened partnerships among government agencies, non-government organizations, cultural institutions, jeepney associations, and local communities. These initiatives are intended to reinforce the identity of the Karatig Jeepney not only as a mode of transportation but also as a symbol of Maloleño heritage.

In addition, preservation efforts focus on maintaining the original form and historical importance of the Karatig Jeepney through museum displays, written documentation, and restoration activities that highlight its cultural and historical evolution. The study also underscores the importance of enhancing public awareness by engaging historians, cultural experts, educators, and community stakeholders in collecting narratives and establishing maintenance guidelines to ensure sustainability. Furthermore, tourism-oriented strategies are proposed to promote the Karatig Jeepney as a unique cultural attraction by developing themed tours, interactive experiences, and collaborative packages with travel agencies, supported by promotional campaigns across digital platforms.

The preservation framework also highlights the establishment of forums, cultural events, storytelling sessions, and school-based collaborations to strengthen community ties and foster appreciation of local heritage. Documentation efforts, including archival research, photography, and oral history collection, are

likewise emphasized to ensure the systematic preservation of its legacy. Moreover, the involvement of local artists through festivals and creative collaborations is encouraged to sustain the artistic identity of the jeepney culture, while educational initiatives aim to facilitate skills transfer and cultural continuity among younger generations. Overall, the findings suggest that preserving the Karatig Jeepney requires an inclusive and sustained effort that balances modernization with cultural conservation, ensuring that it remains a living symbol of Malolos identity for future generations.

Ethical Considerations

The following ethical guidelines were observed throughout the research period. Informed consent was obtained from commuters and drivers before the study commenced, ensuring that participants fully understood the purpose and procedures of the research. Participants were also informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequence. The dignity and well-being of all participants were prioritized and continuously protected during the data collection process. All responses were recorded accurately and were not altered or tampered with to maintain the integrity of the data. In addition, all research data were kept strictly confidential and used solely for the purposes of the study.

Conclusion

The modernization of jeepneys has significantly affected the lives of both drivers and commuters. It is difficult to accept that Karatig Jeepneys must comply with the new policies imposed by the government. However, all thirteen (13) participants expressed disagreement with the phase-out of Karatig Jeepneys, as these vehicles are considered part of their everyday lives and a cultural emblem of the City of Malolos that should be preserved. Based on the analysis of the gathered data, several inferences were made: the government's modernization program should consider the needs of Karatig Jeepney drivers and commuters to improve their welfare; modernized jeepneys have both positive and negative effects on their daily lives; Karatig Jeepneys remain more accessible compared to modernized units but are required to follow government regulations; they also serve as an important socio-cultural symbol that reflects the history and identity of Malolos; modernized jeepneys contribute to addressing environmental concerns such as air and noise pollution; and lastly, the preservation of Karatig Jeepneys should be considered by the local government of the City of Malolos.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, several recommendations are offered. Commuters are encouraged to comply with the government-implemented modernization program and to seek assistance from local authorities if they encounter issues such as increased fares, accessibility, or comfort concerns in transportation. Despite possible financial challenges, jeepney drivers are also advised to comply with the program while actively seeking government support to help assess and address its impact on their operations, recognizing that they are among the most affected stakeholders. The government is likewise urged to conduct informative seminars to properly educate the public about the Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program (PUVMP) and to undertake further studies to fully understand its effects on both drivers and commuters, which may guide improved implementation strategies. Lastly, policymakers are encouraged to prioritize the needs of the masses in crafting and implementing policies, continuously evaluate existing programs for improvement, and consider the cultural significance of jeepneys as part of Philippine heritage to ensure that modernization efforts promote both public welfare and cultural preservation.

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